

Gateway to Population Health Information: Health Information Portal

Sustainability Fact Sheet

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Background

The Health Information Portal (here after as the Portal, <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/>, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8690f1>) was established to provide a centralized gateway, for researchers and policy makers to find population health information, and to enhance the secondary use of health information.

The target audience for the Portal is primarily: researchers in public health and population sciences as well as epidemiologists, statisticians, pharmacists, health professionals, data scientists, ethicists, sociologists etc. Also, data holders and providers, developers in various health information domains, policy and decision-makers in national and international organisations, and others active in the field of public health can be seen as primary users of the material on the Portal. Material can also be of interest to non-governmental organisations and civil societies in the public health and healthcare area, media and journalists, patient organisations, students and educational organisations for population health and health services, as well as the general population, industry and the private sector.

Main outcomes and results

The Portal is built from modules (sections), which can easily be added when needed. These modules include a series of catalogues, following the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) principles and existing metadata standards (Schema.org¹, DDI LifeCycle², DCAT-AP³, and DCAT-AP-Health⁴). The following

catalogues are currently (September 2023) available at the Portal (Figure 1): national nodes in the PHIRI network, data sources, health information projects and initiatives, capacity building activities, COVID-19 related resources, publications, ELSI (ethical, legal, and societal issues), and European research networks, initiatives, and infrastructures. The Portal also provides information on and tools for the PHIRI federated demonstrators and health information system assessments.

Why a centralized portal for health information is needed

The COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated the need for reliable and timely information about different dimensions and determinants of population health to support research and evidence-informed decision making. The Health Information Portal is the first European level portal bringing together a wide variety of population health information. The modular format of the Portal has demonstrated its importance for information sharing among Member States and beyond. In future, the Portal can easily be expanded to include new modules among user community as these emerge.

To ensure the sustainability of the Portal, it is essential to further exploit potential of the Portal to support population health research and evidence-informed decision making. This requires several different elements (Figure 2), the funding being the most important one. More details about sustainability are provided in a specific sustainability report for the Portal.⁵

EXPECTED IMPACT OF THE HEALTH INFORMATION PORTAL

1. To support building stronger Health Information Systems in the Member States.
2. To enhance more effective population health research and respond rapidly to policy issues.
3. To improve capacity building for the public health workforce.
4. To foster more coherent ELSI principles across the Member States in relation to health information use and exchange.
5. To support GDPR compliant multicountry data analysis.

References

- 1 <https://schema.org/>
- 2 DDI. DDI-Lifecycle. 2023. <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Lifecycle/>
- 3 Perego A, Friis-Christensen A, Vaccari L, Tsinaraki C. Using DCAT-AP for research data. 2016. https://www.w3.org/2016/11/sdsvoc/SDSVoc16_paper_27
- 4 HealthData@EU Pilot. Extension of DCAT-AP: HealthDCAT-AP. 2023. https://ehds2pilot.eu/upcoming_results/extension-of-dcat-ap-healthdcat-ap/
- 5 Tolonen H et al. A sustainability roadmap for the European Health Information Portal. 2023. *URL to be added*

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